

Realistic reflection on clinic legal education in China

Lei Li¹, Jieyi Guo², Lin Wang³

¹²³(Guangdong Polytechnic College, Zhao Qing, Guangdong Province, China)

Abstract: Picked clinic law education in China has been 20 years, from the initial attempt to reality and constantly fusion of Chinese traditional law education, injected a large number of Chinese characteristics of legal education, expand the space of legal education in China, to explore a new path for China's law education reform and the development direction of socialist legal system construction in our country. At the same time, in the process of integration with the traditional legal education in China, there are also practical conflicts with the management and educational objectives of colleges and universities. Only a clear understanding of the practical problems of China's clinic legal education, the correct understanding of the essence of China's clinic legal education and value positioning, in order to further promote the organic integration of China's traditional legal theory education and vocational education, to form a systematic, comprehensive, with Chinese characteristics of legal education model will also have far-reaching significance.

Keywords: Clinic legal education ;Law practice teaching; College system; Vocational education

* The research is funded by **The Project of 2019 Innovation and Entrepreneurship for College Students in Guangdong Polytechnic College (Granted number: 2019CXCYYJW002)**&**Guangdong Polytechnic College 2020 Undergraduate Innovation and Entrepreneurship Training Program(Granted number: 202013720002)**.

The construction of socialist legal system with Chinese characteristics cannot be separated from the continuous progress and development of legal education in universities. In recent years, China's legal education in colleges and universities cultivate a large number of excellent legal talents for the society, but with modern law education requirements is still a gap, performance for legal education in colleges and universities personnel training goal ambiguity, the practice teaching of law is weak, the teacher is too theoretical knowledge and so on, the cause of law school graduates lack of professional skills and knowledge reserve can't satisfy the need of society, popular with the social from all walks of life.

With the advent of the new century, clinic legal education, one of the important forms of legal practice teaching in the west, has been introduced into Chinese colleges and universities, aiming to reshape the model of Chinese legal education. After 20 years of practice and exploration, more and more Chinese colleges and universities are learning from the teaching methods of clinic legal education courses to carry out practice teaching. Some scholars point out that the adoption and popularization of this practical teaching method is in line with the objective needs of the development of legal vocational education, the objective laws of legal personnel training, and the correct direction of deepening the reform of China's higher legal education.

I. The practical situation of clinic legal education in China

Clinic legal education from the perspective of practice into the model of legal education, caused great interest in China's legal circle. However, the integration of new things always has a process of colliding with the local culture and social environment and gradually moving towards balance. This process is carried out in contradiction and conflict, and develops in criticism and inheritance. Clinic legal education is no exception, introduced into China for 20 years, there are still many problems. The rational analysis of these problems is helpful to accurately grasp the nature and law of legal education, which is conducive to the steady development of clinic legal education in China.

1.1 The friction between the management system of colleges and universities in China and the legal education of clinics

It is an important trend of China's higher education reform to pay attention to the reform of independent education and the innovation of educational management mode. At present, colleges and universities look forward to reform, but also look forward to the successful reform experience research and reference. The expectation of universities is not conservative. Education itself needs unified guiding ideology, stable school-running environment and school-running mode to ensure the quality of education. Clinic legal education as a new education model, no school has formed a more perfect education paradigm. On the one hand, universities are not well prepared in the conditions of running schools, system guarantee and management operation mechanism. On the other hand, there are certain risks in the process of social investigation and legal proceedings, which run counter to the thought of stability in education management, which is particularly detrimental to the reform of clinic legal education in China.

First, colleges and universities lack in-depth interaction and cooperation mechanisms with the judiciary, legislation and society. Although the state emphasizes the function of colleges and universities to serve the society, it does not require colleges and universities to establish in-depth interaction and communication mechanism with the judiciary, legislation and society. Therefore, it is difficult for colleges and universities to interact and dialogue with the needs and desires of the society. The rigid education and training system of law major lags behind the needs of social development, and the social needs do not feedback to colleges and universities with a good interaction and communication mechanism. University legal education in this closed training system in the trial clinic legal education, the first problem encountered is that the identity of the clinic student agent case is difficult to be recognized. In addition, due to the lack of effective interaction mechanism, for law students lack of practical ability, low employment rate, the society can't recruit the desired legal practice talents and other problems, colleges and universities are often difficult to take effective measures to deal with in time. The hysteresis of education to a certain extent weakens the impetus of reform of law teaching practice and hinders the implementation of clinic legal education model. Due to the lack of interactive mechanism, colleges and universities and judicial, law firms and other units and departments have been difficult to reach cooperation, difficult to establish effective operation of legal practice teaching base and legal clinics, leading to the clinic legal education "hollowing out".

Second, the management and operation mechanism of colleges and universities is not conducive to the reform of the legal education model of clinics. The management mode of colleges and universities in China is generally the three-level management system of schools, colleges and teaching and research offices. Micromanagement is sinking. The management and research work of clinic legal education is concentrated in the law school of colleges and universities and even the teaching and research offices. This kind of authority of rational organization based on responsibility system and centering on power is of positive significance to improve the working efficiency of administrative organization. However, as an institution to cultivate people, colleges and universities have the characteristics of rational organization and should cultivate the diversity and complexity of people more. Education of this kind of particularity, managers will not equal to the administrative organization in colleges and universities, the clinic need a relatively more democratic legal education mode, tolerance to try the academic environment of reform, need and the competent department of education in colleges and universities, the top design and relevant government departments to work together, to coordinate social participation, multiple departments, set up long-term guarantee mechanism. For one thing, not all law schools are in a position to offer clinical law courses. On the other hand, even law schools that can afford to offer the program often fail to fully implement clinical teaching as planned because of funding bottlenecks. In the lack of effective interaction and cooperation mechanism between colleges and society, and the lack of high-level support within colleges and universities, only relying on grassroots teachers to promote and complete the research of clinic legal education is often lack of sustainability and power. Basic education workers lack of operation experience of the reform of education, teaching quality in the initial stage often is not high, clinic operation problems such as lack of scientific, lead to managers in colleges and universities the lack of cognition of practice teaching of law, it is difficult to give more attention and support, not from the school level design

practice teaching reform of law and the overall cohesion between the teaching management.

Third, the university teacher management system is not conducive to the clinic legal education reform experiment. At present, China's colleges and universities generally implement the teacher performance appraisal system based on scientific research achievements, which pays attention to fairness while neglecting the evaluation of teachers' growth process, and lacks a guarantee mechanism for the experiment and research of special education reform. Clinic legal education mode of teacher assessment requirements have changed, in addition to political ideology, education and other hard standards, but also need to work on the enthusiasm of teachers, legal professional responsibility and practical guidance quality assessment. American Bar Association standards stipulate that law schools should provide full-time clinical teachers with the same job security as tenured teachers and give them similar allowances as other full-time tenured teachers, focusing on the protection of practical guidance teachers. Performance for a single evaluation of scientific research in colleges and universities to "baton", did not consider the complexity of student work in the legal practice under the guidance of teachers, there is no incentive practice teachers, peace of mind in the legal education of the clinic work safeguard mechanism, practices type teachers were forced to relax and even give up guide the student to carry on the practice of law, legal clinics had tough situation much worse. By the existing system of introducing talents in colleges and universities, teachers' work management system, teaching quality assessment system and compensation system, the influence of such factors as type of law is difficult to hire right from off-campus practice teaching staff involved in legal clinic education for a long time, only in the internal training way solve the problem of shortage of practical teaching of the teachers. Once young teachers are trained and mature in colleges and universities, they are not willing to engage in the complicated and energetic practical teaching guidance work. Excellent teachers are the key to provide quality education. The current teacher evaluation system in colleges and universities has severed the link between teachers' guiding practice teaching and teachers' professional development, which is not conducive to the reform of clinic legal education.

Fourth, the university personnel training quality evaluation system can't detect the quality of students to accept clinic legal education learning. Clinic legal education by making students receiving party, to provide legal services, writing legal documents, participate in the practice of the conciliation proceedings, not only exercise the students' ability in law practice and innovation ability, also inspects each student's ideological morality and professional ethics, this to improve the quality of talents training provides a good teach viable path. However, the traditional quality evaluation of legal education in colleges and universities in our country mainly focuses on the comprehensive evaluation of students' ideological character, course credits or course scores, which does not include legal practice ability, innovation ability and professional ethics. As a matter of fact, the traditional legal education mode is unable to evaluate the students' ability and professional ethics only by daily study observation and test results, which cannot form an objective and true evaluation and cannot meet the needs of the society for talents. At present, the methods adopted by colleges and universities in practice are mostly based on the empirical evaluation to evaluate students, among which the evaluation of relevant departments and parties is random and fuzzy due to the lack of evaluation standards. There are too many interfering factors in mutual evaluation among students, which makes it difficult to be an effective assessment index. It is difficult for students to complete case reports and papers due to insufficient case sources or unfinished cases, and there are large uncertainty factors, which cannot form effective assessment indicators for comprehensive evaluation of students. Further, there is no scientific demonstration and no authority whether these assessment indicators derived from empirical operations can truly reflect students' legal knowledge, professional skills, professional ethics and social responsibility.

1.2 Analysis of the positioning of the goal of clinic legal education in China

Clinic legal education was introduced into our country as a new teaching mode, teaching method, intended to improve the legal education mode of our country. But in the process of practice, China's legal community found that the most prominent educational goal of the legal education model is vocational education, to cultivate "think like a lawyer" legal professionals. However, the education characteristic of China's civil law system is that it pays attention to cultivating legal research-oriented talents who "think like scholars", which pays attention to theoretical research while neglecting practical teaching and vocational education. The different orientation of

the two educational objectives will inevitably lead to the contradiction and confusion in the practice teaching of teachers.

First, the goal of clinic legal education in China can't change the cultivation of "academic talents". The training mode of legal talents in traditional universities pays attention to the cultivation of students' theoretical foundation and comprehensive quality, emphasizes the function of classroom teaching, pays attention to the cultivation of students' conceptual understanding ability and theoretical logical reasoning ability, and ignores the practical education. Introduce clinic is to change our traditional legal education mode existing in the legal education of students feel dull content, lack of interest in learning, learning ability is insufficient, law intended to reform the classroom teaching contents and curriculum system of legal education, construct to train law student's practice ability and comprehensive quality in the integration of education system, not only pay attention to the accumulation of students' knowledge of legal theory, also emphasized students exercise and improve the ability of using the law; Not only pay attention to the ideological and moral education of students, but also emphasize the cultivation of legal professional ethics of students. However, the society, university administrators and teachers have not reached a consensus on the goal of professional legal education in China and the cultivation of practical skills. Clinic legal education reform attempt, requires the establishment of legal clinics in college talent training institutions, to provide legal aid for the society, and even let students appear in court to participate in legal proceedings. This kind of time-consuming and laborious practical work is not conducive to the cultivation of "advanced knowledge" talents, and will certainly arouse the doubts of "scholar-type" professors. Universities are institutions for the study of advanced knowledge. The idea of academic freedom and academic autonomy has always been the ideological basis for the existence of colleges and universities. While professors are proud of themselves, they are also complacent. The idea of "academic research-oriented" talent cultivation is still deeply rooted in colleges and universities, and the reform of practical teaching methods is regarded as the appendage of theoretical education. In reality, colleges and universities are still in accordance with the theoretical system of law construction of classroom teaching content and curriculum system, clinic legal education only as an elective course for a small range of experiments, can't shake the status of the "college system" teaching model. At the same time, whether it is investigation and evidence collection or legal proceedings, it is not only costly, but also has certain risks and management difficulties, which is unpredictable. In the face of such a realistic problem, education authorities, universities and law schools are difficult to deal with, more difficult to reach the value of identity, hinder the implementation of the legal education model of clinics.

Second, the goal of clinic legal education can't change China's education culture based on theoretical teaching. For many years, the legal education in Chinese colleges and universities has been based on the college education mode of statutory law, which attaches great importance to the concept of legal knowledge and deductive reasoning from concept to form a systematic logical thinking. Clinic legal education mode focuses on legal practice, emphasizing learning from experience, through the practice of learning experience induction, the use of legal logic thinking, that is, "think like a lawyer". , but the reality of law education environment in colleges and universities is still in a paper test of legal theory knowledge as the main evaluation methods, and legal professional qualification exam of our country also pays attention to students' understanding of concepts and laws, pay attention to the knowledge of law and legal theory between logic and reasoning thinking evaluation of law, ignore the attention to the problems of legal practice, to ignore the law under the realistic environment of legal logic thinking, this is even more strengthened the position of "knowledge" of law schools, deepen the influence of legal theory teaching mode.

Third, the goal of legal education in clinics in China cannot change the way students learn. The traditional exam-oriented education model of middle schools in China makes students accustomed to learning in class and subject to the authoritative teaching of book knowledge by teachers, which forms the inertial thinking of students' passive learning and coping with exams. After entering colleges and universities, they are obviously deficient in practical ability and social communication skills. The core concept of clinic legal education is to change the passive way of learning, the combination of legal knowledge and practical application, so that students learn in practice. This requires students not only to have a certain legal knowledge accumulation, but

also in communication ability, cooperation ability, organizational ability and other aspects have a certain quality, in order to meet the practical needs of clinic legal education, at the same time in the process of practice can also improve these comprehensive ability and professional ability, cultivate a sense of social responsibility. But in the real teaching environment, clinic legal education is not only elective courses, but also due to its small size, limited audience, unable to change the majority of students' learning methods, and in the legal clinic learning students still have insufficient ability, rigid learning methods and other phenomena, need teachers to guide and supervise the whole process. The legal profession has a strong realistic orientation. Practitioners are faced with various legal problems contained in the complex society. To solve these problems requires not only extensive humanistic literacy, but also practice and adaptability. Especially for those law students who are interested in the law profession, whether they can provide satisfactory legal services for the parties is the primary criterion for their evaluation, and also the key for law school education to obtain social recognition. The goal of clinic legal education is subject to the reality of education, it is difficult to change the negative impression and evaluation of the society in a short time, and the change of students' learning style is also an urgent problem to be solved in China's education reform.

II. The connotation of clinic legal education in China

For our country's clinic legal education reform, a worrying phenomenon is that, even if the clinic legal education of all kinds of drawbacks have been recognized, but it seems that there is still an invisible force to force our country's legal education in the over-reliance on the legal clinic education errors in the deeper and deeper. Correct orientation of the connotation of clinic legal education in China can help us better study the development direction of clinic legal education.

2.1 The essence of clinic legal education is still legal education

China's clinic legal education with the help of social assistance to provide students with real cases as teaching content, in the process of solving problems to train students' legal professional skills, cultivate their professional ethics and social responsibility. In traditional law teaching, teaching materials are not the whole "facts", teaching content is not the whole of professional ability, teachers do not understand practice, resulting in the disconnection between legal theory and practical legal issues, students lack of practical ability, difficult to meet the needs of the society. The essence of legal education in clinics in China is a form of legal education, which is a practical teaching method used to improve the learning ability of law students. Teachers analyze and screen cases to confirm whether they meet students' practical needs and meet students' learning requirements; Teachers participate in the whole process, which is not only guidance, but also teaching supervision and learning process evaluation. These are consistent with the traditional law classroom education, which are all teaching methods to better cultivate talents.

2.2 The goal of legal education in clinics is to teach students to learn and apply the law

With the rapid development of modern society, new legal provisions are constantly introduced, and the revision and change speed of the original legal provisions is also dizzying. Relying on the traditional teaching method of "college system" to analyze and explain the legal concept and infer the legal logic of students has obviously not kept pace with the development of The Times, even if the teachers engaged in legal education, for the changes of modern law is impossible to fully understand. It is realistic and reliable to cultivate students' legal research methods and legal thinking. From the perspective of educational science, students' acquisition of various legal professional skills cannot be separated from repeated practice around relevant topics in different environments and scenarios. The advantage of clinic legal education is to train students to find problems, research problems and solve problems in real cases in the face of the parties' dilemma. Students learn how to find legal provisions in real cases, how to analyze the connotation of legal theories, how to use law to respond to realistic problems and provide various legal solutions for the parties to find the best solution. More attention is paid to understanding the ethics and value of the legal profession by allowing students to participate in the real legal operation. This also means that the clinic legal education must be with other teaching mode, the integration of the original department law scattered theory, to solve the practical legal problems in the way of integrating students' theoretical knowledge and comprehensive ability, so that it forms a more comprehensive and

systematic learning thinking, grasp the use of legal methods and skills. One of the purposes of legal education reform in our country is to teach law students how to study independently, how to take the initiative to study, how to develop and grow themselves, and to cultivate students to form independent legal thinking mode.

2.3 The teaching method of clinic legal education is integrated

Clinic legal education is the most representative teaching method is interactive teaching method, in addition to the integration of a variety of teaching methods to guide students to practice learning. In the early learning process of the legal clinic, the teacher in addition to the use of traditional teaching method, case teaching method to carry out teaching, but also adopted the simulation, participation, visit type of teaching. In fact, from the moment the students to provide legal advisory services to the society, the clinic legal education activities are targeted to train and cultivate students' legal understanding ability, interpretation ability, use ability and professional ethics as a legal person, so as to improve the students' professional quality of lawyers. In the process of participating in the trial of cases, teachers use interactive teaching, brainstorming and other methods, according to the differences of each student to give targeted guidance, dialogue on practical legal issues, inspire students to deal with the problem ideas, let the students to explore the problem, explain the problem, find the answer. In general, clinical teaching advocates critical thinking, constructive opinions, and a combination of teacher-student interaction and self-assessment, allowing students to identify and correct deficiencies in their thinking. Students' problems and solutions will also prompt teachers to think carefully about the teaching content, constantly adjust and change the teaching methods of legal knowledge, and promote the in-depth development of teaching. Visible, clinic legal education not only brings students an equal, free, harmonious thought field, but also innovates the teaching relationship between teachers and students, let the dull law classroom appear clever lively picture, in the process of dealing with the real problems to cultivate students' fair heart, sense of justice and social responsibility.

2.4 Clinic legal education for the infinite development of students to create opportunities

Clinic legal education provides a new learning platform for law students. In legal clinic class, the students in the face of real cases, contact real party, deep thinking and research all kinds of social problems, to explore the causes of the problem, analysis of how the law and legal theory is applicable to real social relations, to more deeply understand the law, apply the law, to do more creative legal work. Clinic legal education has broken the traditional teaching mode and education space, teachers and students in a free and equal environment to exchange ideas, with real cases to exercise students' thinking. In the real and complex social background, teachers do not cover up and avoid the real problems, share various experiences and methods in the process of handling cases and promote students to participate in the process, help students to form critical thinking, cultivate correct judgment, and create conditions and opportunities for infinite development possibilities for students.

III. The development direction of clinic legal education in China

China has reached a consensus on the problems existing in the traditional legal education mode, and strengthening practical teaching has become an urgent task in the current legal education reform. Several Opinions on the Implementation of the Plan for the Education and Training of Outstanding Legal Talents (Jiao Gao [2011] No. 10) clearly points out that: "Training applied and compound legal professionals is the focus of the implementation of the Plan." The law education should change from the single "general" talent training target to the applied and compound talent training target.

3.1 China's clinic legal education should focus on the humanistic value orientation

Western and Japan and other developed countries will be clinic legal education positioning as a "career orientation", mainly for students after graduation from the undergraduate course. But clinic legal education does not include the humanistic value orientation, it has an irreplaceable role in the cultivation of professional ethics, ethics and social responsibility for students, but the humanistic education in developed countries has been completed in the bachelor stage, the graduate stage focuses on the goal of professional training. At present, the legal clinic education major in undergraduate, and undergraduate education have always been a "liberal"

education, should undertake to the student good academic education and humanities education, to cultivate it into eligible citizen accomplishment, and professional education, make it can use professional talents in the society after graduation, for the lifelong learning and lifelong development lay a solid foundation. However, the reality is not so ideal. The survey on the employment market also shows that more than half of the law graduates in China are not engaged in the legal profession, which is very similar to the situation in continental European countries, and also further confirms the necessity of carrying out broad humanistic education at the undergraduate stage. Therefore, it is scientific to position the humanistic orientation as the training goal of undergraduate stage. In view of the current reality, it is impossible for students in our country to carry out vocational education after the completion of undergraduate education, and we can only increase the content of legal profession education in the current curriculum. The education and training plan of outstanding legal talents in China confirms and points out this point. Is practical and feasible approach, within the law undergraduate education system, increase the types of courses teaching practice, improve practice teaching course credits, extend the practice teaching courses in school, make the practice teaching courses are no longer limited to professional practice, but includes legal clinics, simulation course and so on, many kinds of practical teaching mode.

3.2 China's clinic legal education should be further promoted to become a mass education

Clinic legal education not only put forward higher requirements for teachers, but also on the conditions of running a school, time management, cost management and student conditions have higher requirements, which determines the clinic legal education in the present is only an elite education. But really let all law students benefit from the clinic legal education model, so that each law students have good professional skills, professional ethics and social responsibility is the ultimate goal of legal education. At present, colleges and universities in the process of promoting clinic legal education, encountered teachers, funding and related system protection problems, resulting in its popularity is not high, and more than half of the law students are not engaged in the legal profession, it seems that clinic legal education does not need to be widely popularized. The author thinks, these cannot become clinic legal education only a few students benefit the reason. Students face the social reality in the legal clinic cases, cases of deep thinking behind the phenomenon of law, legal culture, legal system and social system lag, the defects of the existence of problems, need to keep its current exploration, research, reform the problem consciousness, inspire their interest in law, the formation of critical thinking; Guide them to do more creative work, form the thinking mode of finding, analyzing and solving problems; Establish a belief in the rule of law and cultivate their sense of social responsibility. This way of thinking and ethical view is not only of great significance to law students, but also of methodological guidance to every social person to study and solve social problems. It also plays a fundamental role in the construction and development of socialist legal system with Chinese characteristics in the new era. With the deep advance of legal education reform in China's colleges and universities, clinic legal education will be gradually promoted, will let more and more students benefit.

3.3 Clinic legal education reform should be a comprehensive reform of teaching mode

Our country inherits the education system of the Soviet Union, and the legal education is deeply influenced by the tradition of written law education. Clinic legal education model was first introduced into China, only as a practice of legal education in China's legal education reform experiment, is a useful supplement to the traditional legal education. After 20 years of research and exploration, although this understanding has changed, some scholars even proposed to clinic legal education unified legal education curriculum, but the practical level of difficulties, still cannot change the clinic legal education attached to the concept of traditional legal theory teaching. The society and all sectors of education have realized the defects of traditional legal education, so the importance of practical teaching has been promoted to the level of educational strategy for planning. Several Opinions on the Implementation of the Education and Training Plan for Outstanding Legal Talents point out: "Increase the proportion of practical teaching to ensure that the accumulated credits (class hours) in the practice of law are not less than 15% of the total. Strengthen the practical links in school, develop legal method courses, do a good job in case teaching, run a mock court, law clinics, etc. Make full use of the resources of the legal

practice department, build a group of off-campus legal practice teaching bases, actively carry out professional practice with wide coverage, high participation and strong effectiveness, and effectively improve students' legal interpretation ability, legal reasoning ability, legal argumentative ability and the ability to explore legal facts."But now as an important form of clinic practice teaching law education, because of its high standard requirements and the higher education cost, whatever from the coverage of its development and scale in our country, from their courses in law education situation, with the trainee demonstration, simulation course, graduation practice, and other forms of education, is only a part of practice teaching, to comprehensive reform of the law of the education mode of college system.

3.4 China's clinic legal education should pay attention to realize the social function of education

Clinic legal education at the beginning of the orientation of teaching reform is to make up for the shortcomings of traditional legal education. However, the rationality of the initial stage does not represent the long-term development direction of clinic legal education. On the contrary, if we only focus on the campus, do not pay attention to the social function of clinics, do not pay attention to the training of people or citizens (rather than the pure sense of law students), we will be difficult to obtain broad social recognition and support. College students in the new era are not satisfied with the study of theoretical knowledge on campus. The immediacy, interactivity and universality of the network era make the campus further keep pace with the world and society, which requires the clinic legal education in our country to achieve the social function of education. Clinic legal education of our country should keep an open mind, focusing on the judgment and moral still need to pay attention to the social bad phenomenon at the same time, focusing on the rule of law ideal at the same time also need to consider in parts of the rule of law in our country, the backward status quo, pay attention to the combination of the ideal education and practical education, pay attention to the ideological content, theoretical and affinity, promote education pertinence. The continuous development of society requires the constant participation of young people in the transformation of society. They should be the creators and facilitators of society. Clinic legal education not only education students to learn lawyer skills, more important is to educate students to understand the core values of the legal profession, to provide qualified legal services for the parties, to promote social equity, justice and morality, so that students get continuous professional promotion and professional self-development. In addition, the clinic legal education to guide students to pay attention to the community and the countryside, but also has the role of legal publicity, legal services, not only can improve the citizen's awareness of the rule of law and the rule of law literacy, but also can contribute to the construction of the socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics.

Reflecting on the reality of China's legal education, we can find that the goal of China's legal education is shifting from "generalist education" to "professional education". China's legal education, not the introduction of clinical legal education model can change the training mode and training path of legal professionals, social system, communication mechanism, education culture are we cannot ignore the factors; Clinic legal education mode to cultivate the value of students, whether there is a significant impact on students after graduation, the current academic circle has no relevant tracking mechanism and feedback mechanism to study; At present, it is difficult to conclude the value of clinic legal education mode in China's legal undergraduate education stage. But clinic legal education in the face of the real social environment, from doing to learn, learn from experience, pay attention to the real environment of legal deconstruction and problem response, itself is a scientific, rigorous way of legal research, has a strong vitality.

Obviously, this paper is only a basic research work. The road of legal education and research is hard and long, but it is full of justice and power. Research of strengthening the teaching of theory and practice of law, pay attention to cultivate the students' ability to use law and professional ethics, social responsibility and innovation spirit, promote the Chinese traditional legal theory education and the organic integration of vocational education, for China's legal education form system, comprehensive, has the characteristics of education mode will have profound significance.

References:

- [1] Dragon Flying. Research on Clinical Legal Education in China [M]. Beijing: Law Press, 2017.
- [2] Zhao Xinghua. Clinical law education in Japan and its enlightenment to China [J]. Journal of Northeast Normal University (Philosophy and Social Sciences), 2015(6): 236-239.
- [3] Liu Xuedong. [J]. Economic Research Guide, 2016(18): 191-192.
- [4] Jiang Baoguo, Sun Meng. The orientation and development of clinic legal education in China -- a historical and comparative investigation [J]. Journal of Shanxi University of Finance and Economics (Higher Education Edition), 2010(4) : 44-50.
- [5] Li Ao. On the clinical legal education and Confucian academic thought [J]. Law Journal, 2011(8) : 87-90.
- [6] Liu Lei. [J]. Educational Review, 2013(2): 99-101.
- [7] Zuo Weimin, Lan Rongjie. Research on the legal education in clinic [J]. Global Law Review, 2005(3) : 263-269.
- [8] Wang Zhuqing. The evolution of clinical legal education in the United States [J]. Comparative Law Research, 2012(2): 45-55.